

Edible Cities Network – Integrating Edible City Solutions for social, resilient and sustainably productive Cities

EdiCitNet

Deliverable D7.6

Final ECS Curricula, Training Modules and Materials

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Table of Contents

About this document:	2
1. Executive Summary	7
2. Introduction	8
3. ECS Knowledge Pool	12
4. Development - Process and Method	13
5. ECS Curricula and MOOC	19
6. Roadmap to anchor ECS Education	20
7. Training Modules	22
8. Options and examples	28
9. Further ECS Educational Materials	29
Annex	31
Glossary	47
About the EdiCitNet project	48

1. Executive Summary

Throughout the EdiCitNet project, we have been using a broad definition for Edible City Solutions (ECS), which cover a wide range of different forms of urban farming, food production, distribution and consumption. All these ECS are using innovative principles of ecological design, closed resource and energy flows, and provide a wide range of benefits that can be used to make our cities more environmentally-friendly, healthier and more resilient.

In order to integrate ECS into daily urban life and to enable all citizens to make the most out of the Edible City, a certain background and applied knowledge is indispensable. Due to the long history of the Edible City and related practices, the pool of knowledge on ECS is vast, but

Edible Cities MOOC: Cultivating Urban Sustainability

The main ECS curriculum is synthesized in the Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) Making Cities Edible: Cultivating Sustainable Urban Environments. The course objective is to offer and, above all, disseminate practical knowledge on ECS. In a co-creational process involving Communities of Knowledge and Practice, an ECS Knowledge Base was developed using the joint knowledge of all project stakeholders. The content of the course is based on a structured ECS Knowledge Base and holistically addresses the different stakeholders, covering the following main fields: I) ECS Governance, II) Economic value of ECS, III) ECS as Ecological Systems and IV) Socio-cultural impact of ECS. Both the ECS curriculum and the MOOC follow the principles of inclusive communities of shared knowledge

fragmented and not systematically connected to different stakeholder groups and their respective needs. EdiCitNet's educational programme aims to address this issue in order to lower barriers between different knowledge regimes and to facilitate the exchange of knowledge and experiences from different fields. The present report is based on the concept draft developed in D7.4 and promotes the idea of the Edible City and ECS by developing and exploiting different educational formats and materials.

Most importantly, the report advocates for the robust establishment of ECS and the Edible Cities Network, offering an alternative solution to address the tangible obstacles posed by rapid urbanization and enhance city resilience.

and practice, and thus adhere to the Sustainable Development Goals. The deliverable is also a collection of all ECS educational measures that have been developed or compiled during the project. The MOOC is concluded as a co-creation of a structural and holistic knowledge to mainstream ECS as a strategic step towards the development of socially-inclusive, sustainable, productive, biodiversity-friendly, resilient and healthy cities. The deliverable underlines the potential that ECS and the Edible Cities Network itself have to help us face the challenges of rapid urbanisation and global change. In order to efficiently do so, and taking into account that knowledge is in constant flux and development, both the ECS curriculum and the MOOC are easily expandable and can adapt to changing requirements.

2. Introduction

MOOCs, short for Massive Open Online Courses, are online courses available for anyone to enroll free of charge. MOOCs provide an **affordable yet flexible way to learn** new skills and deliver quality educational experiences at scale.

Millions of people around the world use MOOCs

to learn for a variety of reasons, including career development, changing career paths, college preparations, supplemental learning, lifelong learning, corporate eLearning & training, and more.

Making Cities Edible MOOC on Moodle: A fertile and stable soil for ECS Curricula

Throughout the project, we set up the **Making Cities Edible MOOC on the Moodle platform**, which is a free, open-source and modular learning management system written in PHP and distributed under the GNU General Public License. Moodle is used for blended learning, distance education, flipped classroom and other online learning projects in schools, workplaces and beyond. Most importantly, Moodle is used by most universities in the world, offering modular courses. Moodle LMS is the world's most customisable and trusted eLearning solution. Hundreds of millions of people in thousands of educational institutions around the globe use Moodle as a toolbox to manage their online learning.

Moodle is intuitive and user-friendly, making it simple for learners to access course materials and complete assignments. It is accessible from all around the world, meaning the only precondition

for taking a course is to have an internet connection. Due to its modularity, Moodle is able to include additional functionalities to its core platform through the use of plugins. Since everyone can create one, Moodle plugins allow users and organisations to extend and customise its functionality beyond what Moodle itself has developed for core. This flexibility is what makes Moodle collaborative and community-enhanced and allows it to continue growing².

Moodle is often referred to as the most commonly used platform for educational purposes and sharing knowledge. It is adaptable to different languages, and educators can use the modules as part of their own teaching.

This technical background offers a **fertile and stable soil for the ECS Curricula** to be based on. The ECS Curricula offers a structured approach based on the ECS Knowledge Base.

Third Mission and Open Science: inclusive communities of knowledge and practice

Through **third mission approaches and open science**, the universities of tomorrow are opening up to society in a broad sense, to diverse actors seeking vocational training, and to different generations to co-create and care for ecologies of

expertise, i.e., new **inclusive communities of knowledge and practice for the greater public good**. Utilizing this methodology alongside the designated ECS Fields of Knowledge, the MOOC is recognized as a collaborative effort, synthesizing

² Discover the importance of using an open source learning platform like Moodle LMS on their website: <https://moodle.com/about/>, 20.02.2024

comprehensive and interconnected knowledge to promote the integration of Edible City Solutions as a pivotal measure towards fostering

socially inclusive, sustainable, productive, biodiversity-friendly, resilient, and healthy urban environments.

Fig. 1: Benefits and examples of Edible City Solutions (A) ECS Fields of Knowledge (B) according to the ECS concept (e.g., Säumel et al. 2019; Wachtel et al., 2021, Wachtel, T., Reddy, S., Säumel, I., & Niewöhner, J. et al. 2021)

The ECS Fields of Concept are:

I. ECS Governance approach, with shared insights from all of our partners and collaborators regarding practices on successes, and also on mistakes that we can learn from,

II. Economic Evaluation of Edible City Solutions on how to effectively create green jobs, how to save resources, how to reduce food miles and reduce health costs as an example,

III. ECS as Ecological Systems offer environmental benefits such as reducing the effects of the urban heat island or environmental pollution, enhancing biodiversity and the sustainable use of resources.

IV. Socio-cultural impacts of ECS, e.g. the effects and benefits regarding education and participation, improving or fostering local identity and commitment, inclusion and public health (see Fig. 1).

Communities of knowledge & practice: Growing Together - Learning Together

The concept of Edible City Solutions aims to invite citizens to co-create the sustainable development of their society, and to proactively change the urban environment to stakeholders and citizens benefits, and ultimately to induce a paradigm shift

of lifestyle. This transition is facilitated through the comprehensive and co-developed knowledge base within a theoretical and practical context as **Communities of Knowledge and Practice**. The knowledge base is generated within local and regional networks throughout a collective learning

process. We do not rely on specific experts for guidance; instead, we consider each member as an expert in their own right, fostering an environment of mutual respect and collaboration. The MOOC benefits from the contributions of over 200 individuals, including citizens, Edible City Initiatives, small and medium-sized enterprises, various NGOs, public administration entities, and other relevant organizations.

The ECS Curriculum compiles knowledge about Edible City Solutions to different **target groups**, enabling them to appropriate their knowledge to tackle upcoming challenges in their respective cities and contexts. Based on the ECS Fields of Concept and the ECS Knowledge Base, along with several co-creation workshops and evaluation loops, the following target groups were decided upon:

1. People who are curious about the future of cities, who are already part of a community garden or a social initiative and are eager to make the next step to become an Edible City.
2. People who are working for local municipalities or public administration and would like to learn more about

adopting Edible City Solutions into urban planning.

3. People who are working at Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), planning to start an Edible City initiative, a start-up, or (social) business and need guidance on how to do that; who are considering adding a social component to their business and looking for best practices on doing so.

The design draft of the ECS Curricula is the general attempt to transfer the diverse social areas touching upon ECS knowledge into a manageable compilation of learning formats. It caters to different stakeholders and can **support the EU's lifelong learning goals** by accrediting micro-credentials. It lays the groundwork for an international ECS Master's program and provides options for practice-oriented users and newcomers based on their preferences.

As the MOOC "Making Cities Edible" integrates the ECS Fields of Knowledge into **over 100 hours of educational material**, it aims at approaching a basic understanding of the concept of Edible City Solutions and satisfies different interests. Furthermore, it allows for specialization levels.

Fig. 2: Making Cities Edible: Cultivating Sustainable Urban Environments course-view on Moodle with course-menu targeting the different target audiences of the MOOC.

The course integrates the four pillars of the “ECS Education house”: Ecology, Society, Governance and Policy, to support each target groups’ learning about Edible City Solutions:

Ecology: This pillar focuses on the environmental aspects of making cities edible, including topics such as sustainable agriculture, sustainable use of resources, urban farming, green infrastructure, biodiversity, and the impact of food production on ecosystems.

Society: This pillar addresses the social aspects of making cities edible, with topics like community engagement, healthcare, sociocultural environments, social equity in different dimensions, and the role of food in building and sustaining communities.

Governance: This pillar covers the benefits and challenges of becoming an edible city from a governmental perspective, discussing aspects concerning city planning, regulations, decision-making, and co-creation processes related to urban agriculture and promoting sustainable food systems.

Economy: The economic pillar focuses on the financial aspects of making cities edible, including the fundamentals of a circular economy and the impact of social entrepreneurship. It also offers discussions on the economic viability of urban farming, job creation in the agricultural sector, and economic benefits for local communities.

Integrating these four pillars is crucial for creating a **holistic and sustainable approach to making cities edible**. To answer each target audiences’ needs and desired learning outcomes, and to address environmental, social, governance, and economic aspects to ensure a comprehensive understanding and implementation of urban agriculture initiatives, the decision was made to offer the course along the ECS Fields of Knowledge, but to cater for the needs of the different target audiences (Fig. 2). This is how the Apple Tree Model ([Annex 1](#)) for the course was created, offering knowledge through the possibility of further participation and growing together.

Growing Together: Sharing common roots. Exploring different branches. Harvesting fruits of knowledge

The course participants are guided through the basic ECS knowledge by **following the roots and trunk of the tree**. They are learning about the historical context, the fundamentals that guide them, the relevant terminology, ECS influence and interaction with society, and the role of Edible Cities in addressing climate change and adapting to a changing world. Then, depending on which target audience they belong to, participants can choose between **the branches of the tree, catering the various needs and interests** of the different target groups:

1. Community activists and gardeners to follow the path Community-Based (Bottom-Up) Approach
2. Policy makers and urban planners to follow the path Government-based (Top-down) Approach and
3. Start-ups and ECS Businesses to follow the path Business.

At the top of the tree, course participants find **the fruits of knowledge**. Here, each participant's

active contribution will be to share knowledge democratically and equally. This can be done throughout the Edible Cities Network Platform, which has been created throughout the Edible Cities Network project. The platform offers a meeting place for Edible City Solutions, Initiatives and people who are interested in connecting with the growing network of urban changemakers. This Platform also functions as the ECS Knowledge Pool. Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin establishes evaluation loops to critically revise and optimize ECS Curricula, the training modules and the materials with workshops with different target groups, evaluation forms for participants and users and surveys on actualization of emerging needs.

Making Cities Edible: Cultivating Sustainable Urban Environments MOOC on **Moodle**

How to login to the Moodle: **guide**

Information on the MOOC including access link and guide on how to login are also available in the **resources section** on the Edible Cities Network platform.

3. ECS Knowledge Pool

3.1 What is the ECS knowledge pool?

All content which has been integrated into the MOOC and this Deliverable can be found on our Edible Cities Network Platform as well as on external platforms (e.g., Youtube, Spotify). It is a comprehensive co-produced knowledge base with theoretical and practical context as Communities of Knowledge and Practice, generated throughout a collective learning process within the local and regional networks,

through the different working groups within the EdiCitNet project and through relevant contributions from all around the world - **all together over 200 contributors have added their knowledge to the present MOOC.**

3.2 Existing knowledge

The ECS Knowledge Pool can be found on the new Edible Cities Network Platform. The Edible Cities Network Platform stands as a pioneering website

which serves as a dynamic digital hub, consolidating a diverse range of resources, tools, and collaborative spaces tailored to the promotion of sustainable urban food systems and community resilience, fostering knowledge transfer and collaboration. The platform encompasses several key features designed to facilitate engagement, knowledge exchange, and capacity building among stakeholders.

A key feature of the platform is that it functions as a **resource repository**, giving access to a curated collection of resources, like **guidelines, videos, factsheets, openly accessible design tools, and research articles pertinent to strategise, design and plan sustainable urban**

food systems. Registered users can also explore comprehensive insights of best practices, innovative approaches, and case studies from diverse geographical contexts. The Edible Cities Network platform emerges as a transformative resource in the pursuit of sustainable urban development and food system resilience. By leveraging technology, collaboration, and knowledge exchange, the platform catalyzes collective action towards creating greener, healthier, and more equitable cities. The Edible Cities Network Platform is available to browse here: <https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/>

4. Development - Process and Method

Based on the ECS Knowledge Pool, we used a **multi-step approach** for developing and implementing the Making Cities Edible MOOC, ensuring alignment with project goals, the needs of each target group, and best practices in online education. Through each step of the course development, we took **participatory measures** through intensive workshops involving the EdiCitNet consortium as well as members of the target groups.

Each of these steps was built upon the previous step and was followed by review-and evaluation loops in close contact with members of the target groups. First, we **analysed the existing degree programmes and courses** that took place, which covered the research and analysis of similar courses developed to gather insights, best practices, and potential areas for differentiation or improvement ([Annex 2](#)). Based on this, we performed a SWOT-analysis to understand the internal and external factors affecting the MOOC development ([Annex 3](#)). We targeted the following gaps: the lack of a structured and

comprehensive knowledge and a lack of a common language that all stakeholders within an Edible City *own* and *speak*. A common language could offer a holistic approach to dismantle silos of knowledge through various different disciplines.

The roadmap delineated in D7.4 outlines a systematic approach to realizing our educational objectives. In the initial phase, emphasis is placed on the development of the Making Cities Edible MOOC, wherein relevant modules are curated and structured to offer a cohesive educational experience. This foundational step lays the groundwork for subsequent initiatives aimed at broadening the reach and impact of ECS education.

As the next step, we developed the MOOC Business Model Canvas. A Business Model Canvas adapted specifically for the Making Cities Edible MOOC, this canvas outlines key elements such as vision and mission, value proposition, target audience, key activities, resources, partnerships, etc., tailored to the MOOC's context ([Annex 4](#)).

The Edible City Solutions Canvas (ECS Canvas) is a tool developed during the EdiCitNet project. It is an upgraded and calibrated economically sustainable model Canvas for organizations that provide sustainable food solutions within the urban setting. Its predecessor, the Business Model Canvas, is a one-page overview which informs how the key drivers of a business fit together³. Through the project planning, the ECS Canvas was adapted to take into account the fact that not all ECI aim to be a 'business'. This tool consists of 11 segments enabling users to dive deep into various dimensions of achieving economic sustainability to maintain and expand impact.

To fulfill the mission of the "Making Cities Edible" MOOC, we developed a set of target groups. This we implemented through a series of workshops, conducted to identify and define the target audience for the MOOC, as well as to establish clear learning outcomes that the course aims to achieve ([Annex 5](#)).

During the first hybrid workshop, we used a MIRO board as an interactive tool for online collaboration. During this workshop we created "buyer personas", a content marketing strategy tool. A buyer persona is a detailed description of someone who represents a target group. This persona is fictional but based on deep research of our existing or desired audience. After a group discussion, we created the following buyer personas:

1. Urban Food Enthusiast (*Fig. 3*)

- a. Senior citizen who is interested in starting a gardening initiative and gain more income but needs knowledge on building such initiative
- b. Demographics: 60 years old, comes from a working class family
- c. Psychographic: likes gardening (has own allotment garden); wants to be able to have traditional ingredients for feeding her family
- d. Role: Matriarch of the family, influencer of the community
- e. Pain Points: a network of ECI, learn about what is happening in her location
- f. Needs and desires: financial stability and profitability
- g. Barriers and challenges: She has plans, ideas and knowledge but needs help contextualizing and institutional support
- h. This target group is looking for the following skills and knowledge when participating the MOOC Course:
 - Edible Cities techniques
 - How to find and secure funding, scaling, how to achieve social impact
 - Mentoring from practitioners, getting feedback from them
 - By the end of the course, she would like to set up her own project

³ Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture - Playbook. By Idil Akdos, Alexander Schabel, Adam Curtis, Suhana Reddy. On

EdiCitNet Website. <https://www.edicitnet.com/wp-content/uploads/GJUA-Playbook-190521.pdf>, 10.07.2023

Fig. 3: Group 1 was working on the “Urban Food Enthusiast” Target Audience.

2. Decision Maker/Urban Planner (Fig. 4)

- a. Teacher/Director of a school, who wants to incorporate ideas about ECS but doesn't know where to start from
- a. Demographics: 35 years old, single, academic background, middle class
- b. Psychographic: likes gardening, climbing and political activism; wants to give children important life skills, likes to engage with people politically; wants to make the world a better place; takes part in activists and gardening groups
- c. Role: Influencer
- d. Pain points: strict Curricula, applying knowledge to school

- e. Needs and desires: networking, getting knowledge about gardening in schools
- f. Barriers and challenges: working with parents, explaining the values of Edible City Solutions
- g. This target group is looking for the following skills and knowledge when participating in the MOOC Course:
 - To be able to use different tools to network effectively,
 - To communicate the worth of ECS to school and governors.

The third target audience (business) was added after a revision loop of the target audiences.

Fig. 4: Group 2 was working on the “Decision maker” Target Audience.

As a conclusion, participants agreed that all target groups are looking for similar skills and knowledge while enrolling for the EdiCitNet MOOC.

This was the starting point of the second “Intended Learning Outcomes for the MOOC” workshop (Annex 6), using again a MIRO board. Following the “Backward design methodology”⁴, the workshop participants first worked on the “Intended Learning Outcomes” then formed three groups and worked on the acceptable evidence, assessment and learning activities.

By defining the Intended Learning Outcomes, first we defined the goals or intended learning outcomes for the course, taking the form “By the end of this course students will be able to [active verb]...” By using active verbs, we articulated actions that students will be able to do. These actions can be observed and compared with our desired results; and it also puts the focus on students, as it is not “By the end the course the instructor will have...”, and advances the ultimate

goal of backward design – to facilitate learning, not simply to “cover” content.

The Intended Learning Outcomes for the EdiCitNet MOOC are also the skills and knowledge participants are looking for when they partake in the MOOC:

- By the end of the course, students will have an Edible Cities network.
- By the end of the course, students will be aware of Edible City methodologies.
- By the end of the course, students will be able to work on their own Edible Solutions or Initiative.
- By the end of the course, students will be able to achieve social impact.
- By the end of the course, students will understand the value and worth of working with ECS.

Then in groups, with the help of a set of questions, we worked on the assessment and

⁴ Backward design, MIT Teaching and Learning Lab, [Where to Start: Backward Design | Teaching + Learning Lab \(mit.edu\)](https://teaching.mit.edu/backward-design/), 5.7.2023

to a scope of 210 webinars, presentations, factsheets, podcasts, articles and academic papers and presentations recorded through

conferences and summer schools, to be added to the MOOC, a structured approach following the needs of the three different target audiences.

Growing together

Fruits

Sharing your harvest is caring: By participant's active contribution will be sharing knowledge democratically and equally and without geographical borders.

Branches

Cater to the various needs and interests of the different course participants:

- Community activists and gardeners > Community-Based (Bottom-Up) Approach
- Policy makers, urban planners > Government-based (Top-down) approach
- Start-ups and ECS Businesses > Business

Roots and Trunk

- Exploring the historical context
- Fundamentals that guide them
- Relevant terminology,
- Influence and interact with society,
- Role of Edible Cities in mitigating climate change

Fig. 6: The MOOC's Apple Tree Model.

Based on the target audiences' preferred learning objectives, we developed the Apple Tree Model (Fig. 6) to find the common points between target groups, their learning objectives and ECS Knowledge Pool. The Apple Tree Model refers to a structural model for organizing the content of the MOOC, inspired by the metaphor of an apple tree, representing branching out into different topics based around the needs of each target group.

The Apple Tree Model offers an attempt to structure the ECS Knowledge base and the four pillars holding the ECS Curricula. The roots and the trunk are exploring the basic structure and fundamentals of the Edible City, while the branches cater to the various needs and interests of the different course target audiences, with 3 different

chapters offering optional content for the three target audiences: policymakers, urban planners, community activists, and the general public. Each branch could delve deeper into the aspects most relevant to its audience and are optional to take. The fruits of the tree symbolise each participants' knowledge, while the tree as a growing organism refers to the participant's active contribution by uploading tasks and projects, setting up and taking part in discussions, and sharing tips and resources with their peers.

As the next step, a detailed syllabus for the MOOC was developed, based on the content and knowledge identified in the ECS Knowledge Pool, the Target Groups, and the Apple Tree Model (Annex 9). The MOOC syllabus enabled us to target

the missing knowledge base(s) serving the needs of the target audiences. As gaps were identified in the existing knowledge pool, it was necessary to engage project partners and subcontractors to create the necessary content missing from the ECS Knowledge Pool. As the final step, before creating

the MOOC on the Moodle platform, we reformulated the content with techniques that are commonly employed in marketing (marketing copywriting) aiming to appeal to specific target groups.

5. ECS Curricula and MOOC

Building upon the foundational principles of the 4 Pillars-Model (Social, Economic, Ecological, Governmental), we propose the development of an ECS Curriculum that encompasses the breadth and depth of knowledge essential for addressing contemporary urban food system challenges.

We chose a structured Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) that we named "Making Cities Edible: Cultivating Sustainable Urban Environments" and which was launched on February 15th through an online webinar with over 100 participants and speakers from the EdiCitNet project itself. As described already, the course addresses different stakeholders being involved as target groups, such as people volunteering in community gardens and/or working at various Edible City Initiatives, working at the local Governance level, and planning a Business with an Edible City Solution - academia and non-academia likewise. Drawing inspiration from the pedagogical insights and established practices in other academic disciplines, our **ECS Curriculum adopts a modular structure designed to facilitate comprehensive learning experiences.**

Similar to the approach employed in other disciplines and courses at universities, the ECS Curriculum is structured around core thematic areas, each corresponding to one of the four pillars of Edible City Solutions. Within each thematic area, students engage with interdisciplinary content spanning ecological, social, economic, and political

dimensions, thereby gaining a holistic understanding of ECS dynamics. Furthermore, the ECS Curriculum embraces a learner-centered approach, offering flexibility and customization to accommodate diverse learning styles and interests. Students have the opportunity to select elective content and engage in experiential learning activities, such as fieldwork, internships at for example community-based projects, to deepen their understanding of specific topics and apply theoretical knowledge in real-world contexts. Moreover, the ECS Curriculum adopts a competency-based assessment framework, wherein students are evaluated based on their mastery of key competencies relevant to sustainable urban food systems. Assessment methods include written assignments, presentations, group projects, and reflective portfolios, enabling students to demonstrate their ability to analyze complex issues, develop innovative solutions, and communicate effectively. By adopting a modular structure, learner-centered approach, and competency-based assessment framework, the ECS Curriculum aligns with established pedagogical principles while offering a novel and dynamic educational experience tailored to the complexities of sustainable urban food systems. Through continuous refinement and innovation, we endeavor to cultivate a cohort of ECS graduates equipped with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to effect positive change in urban environments worldwide. This ECS Curriculum forms the MOOC, which is based on the

extensive knowledge created throughout the EdiCitNet Project lifetime (see ECS Knowledge Pool) and is created through participatory and co-

creation methods (described in Development Process and Methods).

6. Roadmap to anchor ECS Education

The Edible Cities Network endeavors to anchor its **educational initiatives beyond the academic landscape, fostering the integration of essential knowledge** pertaining to sustainable urban food systems across various disciplines. This chapter outlines a roadmap and implementation strategy derived from deliverable D7.4, focusing on the development and dissemination of ECS education.

Moodle is a popular open-source learning management system (LMS) that is often used to create massive open online courses (MOOCs). It provides **a platform for educators to create online courses, manage course materials, interact with students, and assess their progress**. Many educational institutions, corporations, and organizations use Moodle because of its **flexibility, scalability, and customizable features**. The “Making Cities Edible” MOOC created on Moodle is an organized course content, with the **possibility of facilitating communication and collaboration among participants, and tracked learning progress through various assessment tools**. As most of the EdiCitNet project’s academic collaborators use Moodle as their LMS (e.g., University of Ljubljana, University of Lomé, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin), the current MOOC creates a strong base for upscaling the course to an academic level as its modules can be part of the academic curriculum. In Moodle, **users can access sections or modules based on their interests** and backgrounds by navigating through the course structure. For example, a student with a humanities background may navigate directly the chapter focusing on the socio-cultural impact of ECS. Those interested in governance can find relevant materials under the chapter discussing ECS governance frameworks. Learners with an economics perspective can access

resources and activities centered around the economic valuation of ECS. By organizing the ECS knowledge base in Moodle according to these perspectives, we can provide learners with tailored learning experiences that cater to their interests and educational objectives. In Moodle, the course content and resources are organized related to the ECS (Ecological Systems) knowledge base according to different perspectives such as humanities, ecological, governance, and economics. Within Moodle, the structure and access to the ECS Knowledge Base is possible from these various perspectives:

Built upon the pillar “**ECS and Society**”, the chapter “Community-Based (bottom-up) Approach” caters to the needs of course participants arriving from the Humanities Perspective. This chapter offers **readings, case studies, and discussions exploring the socio-cultural impact of ECS**. Here, various presentations and masterclasses offer multimedia content, such as videos or podcasts, highlighting the relationship between human societies and ecological systems, as the bottom-up approach involves starting with individual components or details and gradually building up to the overall system or concept. It emphasizes the importance of understanding the specific elements before analyzing their interactions and is **focussing on community empowerment and grassroots initiatives**, drawing attention to their unique cultural, social, and economic dynamics. A bottom-up approach allows citizens to take charge of their environmental conditions, fostering a strong sense of ownership, identity, and a feeling of community within neighborhoods. Despite its citizen-driven tactics, the approach can often lead to fragmented development, inadequate infrastructure, and

challenges when facilitating large-scale projects.

This chapter includes over **35-hours of learning materials** is especially designed for urban gardening enthusiasts, who are already taking part in a grassroots initiative and are wishing to become a key player in greening their local environment, who want to strategize and strengthen their organization by building a strong network of different project stakeholders, becoming an equal partner for the local municipality.

Built upon the pillar “**Governance and Policy**”, the chapter “Government-based (top-down) Approach” offers structured and tailored sources of knowledge for course participants arriving from the governance, local municipalities or city planning. This chapter offers the course materials, such as **scientific papers, technical reports, documents, articles, several multimedia resources** e.g., videos and podcasts and case studies discussing different governance structures and strategies for managing ECS, simulations and a design and planning tool related to the governance and management of ecological systems. The chapter also offers **quizzes to reinforce technical concepts and skills** related to ECS and also facilitates discussions and assignments where learners analyze and critique existing ECS governance frameworks. The bottom-up and top-down approaches are two contrasting methods of problem-solving, management, and system design. These approaches represent different ways of understanding and addressing complex issues. The top-down approach involves starting with the larger picture which is then broken down into smaller components. It focuses on the overall structure and organization before delving into the specifics. It is associated with governing bodies that hold the authority to shape a city's trajectory. This approach can bring efficiency, modernization, and cohesion to urban spaces. However, they can also fail to capture the essence of local neighborhoods and their nuanced needs.

This chapter includes over **60-hours of learning materials** and is especially designed for people representing a local municipality willing to broaden their knowledge about an Edible City, city planners working towards a greener, edible, and resilient city and are interested in lessons learned on sustaining an Edible City and involving and strengthening stronger communities.

Built upon the pillar “**ECS and Economy**”, the chapter “Business - Ways to Monetize your Knowledge and Create an Impact” offers curated resources for course participants arriving from the economics perspective. This chapter's offer is based on resources such as **economic models, cost-benefit analyses, market-based instruments and case studies and several multimedia resources** e.g., videos and podcasts related to ECS. The chapter offers activities where learners assess the economic value of ecosystem services and explore sustainable economic practices.

In this chapter, including over **22-hours of learning materials**, the **essence of social entrepreneurship and social innovation is uncovered** along with its combining business insights with a commitment to addressing societal challenges. Through the business chapter, participants are delving into the key concepts and strategies that not only **empower them to monetize their expertise but also enable them to make a meaningful impact on society**. This chapter is curated aiming to target the needs of small or medium-sized business owners, and start-uppers, planning to monetize their knowledge based on Edible City Solutions. The chapter includes practices on how to create a sustainable business model consisting of a vision and a mission, alongside a strategy for your business or would like to develop their already existing business model. They are eager about the challenges they are facing and are interested, how collaboration and co-creation increase the success and sustainability of their project. They are also interested to find out and read best practices on the possible adaptation strategies for different

political and business ecosystems.

Followed by the outline and the structure of the course, the chapter “Introduction to Edible Cities” is built on the pillar “**Ecology**” and it creates a basis for all the above chapters for all participants arriving from different perspectives. This chapter, with over **35-hours of course material**, creates a stable ground of understanding and common language for all different disciplines learning about

Edible Cities. Topics from History of Urban Food Production, Fundamentals and Terminology, the Impact of Edible Cities on Society, Edible Cities as a Measure Against Climate Change to Bottom-up vs. Top-down approaches serve for building a strong common basis on ECS. In the Making Cities Edible course, each chapter is followed by a **resource list, a quiz, recommended tasks and a summary**. After the completion of each entry, a certificate can be generated (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7: MOOC Certificate for completing activities related to the chapter “Community-Based (Bottom-Up) Approach”

7. Training Modules

In the endeavor to implement Edible City Solutions (ECS), it is imperative to ensure that all training modules encompass a thorough examination of the four pillars and the diverse stages of ECS life cycle, namely Development, Implementation, and Maintenance. This process involves scrutinizing existing training modules for completeness and relevance, and where necessary, supplementing

with new content. The following part outlines the structure and content of the training modules, incorporating the essence of ECS and its significance within urban environments.

The Apple Tree Model which we applied for the MOOC offers a structured attempt to ECS Knowledge Pool based on the ECS Knowledge Fields and the four pillars forming the structure of

the ECS Curricula.

General Module: Defining the Nature of ECS

The General Module on Defining the Nature of ECS provides an academic exploration of sustainable urban development paradigms. Delving into the fundamental principles and significance of ECS within urban contexts, this module examines its economic aspects, resilience strategies, sustainable urbanism frameworks, and theories of social inclusion. Through a historical lens, students gain insights into the emergence of ECS as a critical paradigm in urban planning and development agendas. Furthermore, the module offers a critical analysis of theoretical underpinnings and practical applications of ECS, utilizing case studies to elucidate successful implementations across diverse urban settings. Grounded in academic rigor, this module equips students with analytical tools to navigate challenges and opportunities in contemporary urbanization processes, fostering a deeper understanding of ECS as a holistic approach

to ecological resilience, social equity, and economic prosperity within cities.

Followed by the chapter “General Introduction” offering an overview on the general concept of Edible Cities, and the four pillars as the main ECS Knowledge Base, with an outline and structure of the course, the description of the target audiences and how they find the content interesting for them in the Apple Tree Model, and an introduction to the EdiCitNet project, the course tutors and contributors and a short introduction to the Edible Cities Network Platform, this module is represented in the Apple Tree Model with the Root system. As a stable base of the tree, thriving on ground full of nutrients, this chapter is called “Introduction of Edible Cities” and it consists of sub-chapters like “Brief History of Urban Food Production”, “Fundamentals and Terminology” related to edible cities and “Impact of Edible Cities on Society”.

The screenshot shows the Moodle course interface. At the top, there are navigation links: Moodle-Helps, Dashboard, My courses, and Courses. On the right, there are icons for notifications, chat, and a user profile. The main content area is titled 'Add topic' and shows a dropdown menu for 'Introduction to Edible Cities'. The left sidebar contains a list of course topics, with 'Introduction to Edible Cities' selected and highlighted in blue. The main content area displays a large image of a rooftop garden with various plants and vegetables, set against a backdrop of a city skyline under a cloudy sky.

Fig. 8: Making Cities Edible course view with the chapter “Introduction to Edible Cities”

Module: Ecological Systems

The Ecological Systems module provides an introduction to urban agriculture and its ecological significance within the framework of ECS. Students explore guidelines for crop cultivation, water management, nutrient cycling, and soil health to optimize agricultural practices within urban environments. Additionally, strategies for enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services are examined to promote ecological resilience and sustainability. By delving into the ecological principles underlying ECS and their implementation strategies, students gain a comprehensive understanding of how urban agricultural initiatives can contribute to the broader goals of ecological sustainability and urban resilience.

This module is covered in the chapter “Introduction to Edible Cities”, that discusses the role of Edible Cities in mitigating climate change, focusing on sustainable and

eco-friendly practices, and explores both grassroots initiatives (bottom-up) and governmental or institutional efforts (top-down) in promoting Edible City Solutions.

The chapter “Introduction to Edible Cities” is built on the pillar “Ecology” and it creates a basis for all participants arriving from different perspectives. This chapter with 35-hours of course material, creates a stable ground of understanding and common language for all different disciplines learning about Edible Cities. “Introduction of Edible Cities” chapter is split up catering both the needs of the General Module as the root system and the trunk from the Apple Tree Model, for all three target audiences.

As in the Apple Tree Model, the branches cater to the various needs and interests of the different course participants, covering chapters with

optional content for the three target audiences: policymakers, urban planners, community activists, and the general public, each participant can decide, that based on their interests, which pathway (different modules) of the course they want to follow. Each pathway or branch of the tree represents a module and offers content curated to meet each participant’s needs. Regardless, which option they choose, participants meet at the end of each module, at the extracurricular chapter. This chapter is funneling participants’ growing attention towards the Edible Cities Network Platform, offering an online space for connecting, networking and sharing knowledge. The chapter “Conclusion” offers a short overview on the learnings with the possibility for the participants to generate a certificate upon each module's completion.

Module: Social Impact

The Social Impact module delves into the assessment of social impact and evaluation methodologies within the realm of ECS. Students examine strategies for establishing and maintaining ECS initiatives, with a particular focus on fostering social inclusion and accessibility. Through theoretical exploration and practical case studies, this module explores the social dimensions of ECS projects and their impact on communities. By analyzing the intersection of social dynamics and sustainability initiatives, students gain insights into effective strategies for promoting equitable and inclusive urban development within the context of ECS.

Built upon the pillar “ECS and Society”, the chapter “Community-Based (bottom-up) Approach” caters to the needs of course participants learning from the Humanities Perspective.

The screenshot shows a Moodle course interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Moodle-Helps', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Courses'. The left sidebar contains a navigation menu with the following items: 'General Introduction', 'Introduction to Edible Cities', 'Community-Based (Bottom-Up) Approach' (highlighted), 'Social Values', 'Adaptation Strategies for Different Socio-Cultural Environments', 'What is Scaling? (Up)scaling Pathways', 'Resources', 'Practical Guidelines for Communities and Community Organizers', 'Quiz on the community based (bottom up) approach', 'Task', 'Summary', 'Government-Based (Top-Down) Approach', 'Business - Ways to Monetize', and 'your Knowledge and Create Impact'. The main content area shows the title 'Community-Based (Bottom-Up) Approach' and a photograph of a group of people sitting around tables outdoors in a garden setting, engaged in a community meeting or workshop.

Fig. 9: Making Cities Edible course view with the chapter “Community-Based (bottom-up) Approach”

Module: Governance

The Governance module offers an in-depth analysis of governance dynamics and structures within the context of ECS. Students explore the intricate dynamics of governance, identifying key stakeholders and their roles in the implementation of sustainable urban development initiatives. Through the examination of strategies for effective governance and collaboration, students gain insights into the essential governance structures necessary for successful ECS implementation. By

delving into theoretical frameworks and practical case studies, this module equips students with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate complex governance challenges and foster collaborative approaches towards building ecologically sustainable and resilient cities. Built upon the pillar “Governance and Policy”, the chapter “Government-based (top-down) Approach” offers structured and tailored sources of knowledge for course participants arriving from governance, local municipalities or city planning.

The screenshot shows the Moodle course interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Moodle-Helps', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Courses'. The left sidebar contains a navigation menu with the following items: 'General Introduction', 'Introduction to Edible Cities', 'Community-Based (Bottom-Up) Approach', 'Government-Based (Top-Down) Approach' (selected), 'The Benefits of Becoming an Edible City', 'Co-Creation as a New (Complementary) Form of Governance', 'Challenges in Urban Planning addressed by ECS', 'Governance', 'Education and Working with Youth', 'Practical Guidelines for the City Administration', 'Resources', 'Quiz on the Government-Based (Top-Down) Approach', 'Task', and 'Summary'. The main content area shows a presentation slide titled 'Sprouting Oslo' with the following text:

- 2010 → Urban agriculture on the political agenda
- 2017 → Agency for Urban Environment gets the political order to develop Oslo's strategy for urban agriculture
- 2019 → The City Council adopts the strategy

The slide also includes a photo of a person working in a garden.

Fig. 10: Making Cities Edible course view with the chapter “Government-based (top-down) Approach”

Module: Economic Value

The Economic Value module offers a comprehensive exploration of the triple bottom line approach, encompassing social, environmental, and economic aspects within the context of ECS. Students delve into the creation and translation of value propositions, identifying strategies to balance economic viability with social and environmental considerations. Through an examination of economic perspectives, job creation opportunities, and innovative business models in urban agriculture, participants gain insights into harnessing

economic potential within sustainable urban development initiatives. Additionally, the module examines the economic dimensions of ECS, focusing on strategies for value creation and sustainability to promote long-term prosperity and resilience within urban environments. Built upon the pillar “ECS and Economy”, the chapter “Business - Ways to Monetize your Knowledge and Create an Impact” offers resources for course participants arriving from the economics perspective.

The chapter Governance-Based (Top-Down) Approach provides an in-depth exploration of the concept of Edible Cities and their role in urban development.

Business - Ways to Monetize your Knowledge and Create Impact

Detail of the interior of Platten Baum's Mini-Biosphere - a mobile greenhouse designed for urban space

Fig. 11: Making Cities Edible course view with the chapter “Business - Ways to Monetize your Knowledge and Create an Impact”

enhancing project success and sustainability, while adaptation strategies for diverse political and business ecosystems are discussed.

The EdicitNet Platform (Extracurricular)

The world's meeting place for sustainable urban food systems and green edible cities

53 Solutions, 66 Initiatives, 5 Communities, 311 Users

The Edible Cities Social Network

Fig. 12: Making Cities Edible course view with the extracurricular chapter “The EdiCitNet Platform”

Each course chapter provides a comprehensive list of resources for participants to deepen their knowledge and offers a summary that distills the key points of the chapter. This section will serve as a quick reference for participants to reinforce their understanding. Furthermore, each chapter

has an assessment component consisting of a quiz and a practical task. The quiz tests participants' theoretical knowledge gained from the chapter. The task is designed to be hands-on, ensuring participants not only grasp theoretical concepts but also apply them in practical

scenarios. Course participants' active contribution by uploading your tasks and projects, setting up and taking part in discussions, and sharing your tips and resources with us and your peers, will be sharing knowledge democratically and equally and without geographical borders.

D7.6 aims to provide a comprehensive framework for implementing ECS training

modules, ensuring alignment with the core principles and objectives of urban sustainability and resilience. By embracing diverse perspectives and experiences, the training modules will empower students to navigate the complexities of ECS implementation and contribute effectively to the transformation of urban landscape.

8. Options and examples

As a future step, the course could be accredited to the European approach to **micro-credentials for lifelong learning and employability**. An effective culture of lifelong learning is key to ensuring that everyone has the knowledge, skills and competences they need to thrive in their personal and professional lives. Micro-credentials certify the learning outcomes of short-term learning experiences, for example a short course or training. They offer a flexible, targeted way to help people develop the knowledge, skills and competences they need for their personal and professional development. Shorter forms of learning opportunities than traditional qualifications, such as micro-credentials, are being developed rapidly across Europe and around the world. These opportunities are made available by a wide variety of public and private providers in response to the demand for more flexible, learner-centered forms of education and training. They also have the potential to offer education and training opportunities to a wider range of learners, including disadvantaged and vulnerable groups.

Throughout the second step, we focus on the dissemination of ECS knowledge through the integration of modules into existing degree programs. By rescaling the comprehensive approach into modular units, we facilitate the incorporation of ECS content into a diverse array of

disciplines, including Urban and Physical and Human Geography, Urban Anthropology, Urban Sociology, and Natural Resource Management. This strategy enables the seamless integration of ECS knowledge into the fabric of the university landscape, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Furthermore, the roadmap underscores the importance of leveraging existing cross-disciplinary programs, such as Studium Oecologicum (a ring lecture at Humboldt Universität zu Berlin) and Studium Generale, as well as lifelong learning degree programs tailored to adult learners with professional experience. By embedding ECS modules within these frameworks, we democratize access to ECS education and cater to a broader audience of learners.

In the final phase, we leverage insights garnered from teaching experiences to advance towards the establishment of a standalone ECS degree program. This endeavor represents a significant milestone in our educational journey, offering students the opportunity to specialize in ECS and obtain accredited qualifications. Moreover, it sets the stage for collaborative endeavors, such as the development of an ERASMUS Mundus EMJMPs proposal, aimed at fostering international cooperation and exchange in ECS education.

Circle U Initiative

In alignment with our educational roadmap, we are actively engaged in the Circle U initiative, a collaborative endeavor involving multiple European universities committed to advancing sustainability and societal resilience. Through Circle U, we seek to leverage synergies and share best practices in ECS education, thereby catalyzing transformative change at both local and global scales. Initial steps and outcomes of our involvement in the Circle U initiative are described below.

In conclusion, the roadmap outlined herein represents a strategic framework for advancing ECS education within the academic sphere. By fostering collaboration, innovation, and inclusivity, we aim to cultivate a new generation of leaders equipped with the knowledge and skills to address the complex challenges facing our urban environments. Through concerted efforts and partnerships, we endeavor to realize the vision of sustainable and resilient cities anchored in principles of equity, biodiversity, and community well-being.

9. Further ECS Educational Materials

Throughout the project, we have created various educational and informational materials from Summer Schools, handbooks, educational materials for children and youth, podcasts, articles, city posters, presentations, guides, webinars, explanation videos, masterclasses, publications, and workshop materials. All of these materials outline the diverse range of educational and informational materials produced within the framework of The Edible Cities Network.

The presentations recorded during the **Summer Schools** held in 2021 and 2022 serve as immersive learning experiences for participants interested in urban sustainability and food systems. These programs offered a range of workshops, lectures, and hands-on activities aimed at fostering knowledge exchange and skill development. Participants had the opportunity to engage with experts in the field, collaborate in projects, and gain practical insights into sustainable urban planning and food production and serve as a comprehensive guide for participants of the MOOC.

Comprehensive **handbooks and factsheets** provide practical guidance on various topics, from creating podcasts and organizing co-creation workshops to

implementing community events and lessons learned from the master planning processes facilitated through the EdiCitNet project. These resources serve as valuable tools for individuals and organizations seeking to initiate and sustain Edible City Solutions and Initiatives, offering best practices, tips, and lessons learned from previous experiences.

Educational materials tailored for educators and social workers, designed to raise awareness and instill a sense of environmental stewardship from a young age. These materials utilize engaging activities, stories, and interactive content to teach children about the importance of urban agriculture, healthy eating habits, and sustainable living practices

Podcasts and articles provide platforms for in-depth discussions and analyses of key issues related to urban sustainability and food security. Expert interviews, research insights, and community perspectives are shared through these mediums, fostering dialogue and knowledge dissemination within the Edible City network and beyond.

City showcases serve as visual representations of successful ECS Initiatives and living lab showcases.

These posters highlighted innovative projects, community collaborations, and tangible outcomes, inspiring others to replicate and adapt similar approaches in their own urban contexts.

Presentations delivered during the Edible Cities Network conferences and Final Meeting, provided opportunities for researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders to share their findings, experiences, and recommendations. These presentations cover a wide range of topics, including urban agriculture, food policy, community engagement, and sustainable development, contributing to a collective understanding of challenges and opportunities in the field.

Guidelines and webinars offer practical support and expert advice for Edible City Solutions Initiatives, covering topics such as project management, stakeholder engagement, dissemination and evaluation. These resources equip participants with the tools and knowledge needed to navigate the complexities of urban food systems and implement effective interventions.

Explanation videos and masterclasses provide in-depth insights into various aspects of urban planning, lobbying, and advocacy. Accompanied by factsheets and podcasts, these multimedia resources offered a comprehensive learning

experience, catering to diverse learning styles and preferences.

Publications and workshop materials disseminate research findings, case studies, and practical tools serve as valuable references for academics, policymakers, and practitioners seeking evidence-based solutions to urban food challenges.

By adopting a multi-modal approach and considering the needs and preferences of individuals with different types of memory, **the MOOC offers an inclusive learning environment.** For the ones with a visual memory, visual storytelling with images and videos help to convey information. People with an auditory memory can opt for audio elements, such as podcasts and recorded lectures. The MOOC also offers transcripts and captions for audio content to assist individuals with hearing impairments or for those who prefer reading. For participants with an audiovisual memory, visual and auditory elements are combined in multimedia presentations to create memorable learning experiences. Interactive elements such as quizzes, and hands-on activities engage multiple senses and promote deeper memory encoding. Hence, the MOOC can effectively serve a diverse audience and enhance engagement, comprehension, and retention of information.

Annex

1. MOOC Structure: Apple Tree Model (Annex 1)

The “Making Cities Edible” course`s tree structure

SHARING YOUR HARVEST IS CARING

As a tree is an organically growing structure, we will grow the knowledge of this MOOC together, too. By your active contribution by uploading your tasks and projects, setting up and taking part in discussions and sharing your tips and resources with us and your peers, you will be sharing knowledge democratically and equally and without geographical borders.

BRANCHES

The branches cater to the various needs and interests of the different course participants, covering chapters with curated content for policymakers, urban planners, community activists and the general public. Each branch could delve deeper into the aspects most relevant to its audience and are optional to take. The three branches are the following:

- Community-based (bottom-up) approach. This chapter is intended for community organisers and provides practical guidelines to harness the power of collectives.
- Government-based (Top-down) approach. This chapter provides practical guidelines for city administrations, covering various aspects such as governance principles, urban planning, building-integrated urban agriculture and the cultivation of public spaces.
- Business.

This chapter is intended for people interested in setting up or developing their business based on Edible City Solutions.

ROOTS & TRUNK

The roots are exploring the historical context of Edible Cities, the fundamentals that guide them, and the relevant terminology.

The trunk is examining how Edible City Solutions influence and interact with society, addressing potential benefits and challenges. It discusses the role of Edible Cities in mitigating climate change, focusing on sustainable and eco-friendly practices and explores both grassroots initiatives (bottom-up) and governmental or institutional efforts (top-down) in promoting Edible City Solutions.

2. Analysis of Courses developed by sister projects and other players (Annex 2)

Lund University MOOC on Urban Nature: Connecting Cities, Sustainability and Innovation - <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1N5AYeOzfV6inl3YI4ptJVxgJq02IfwhjXMaR958NvcM/edit?usp=sharing>

Other NBS MOOCs (NATURVATION, progireg, MOOC Climate Change and Resilience in Food Systems, Food Systems & Climate Change - Sustainability Course - FutureLearn + Free Online

Environment & Nature Courses - FutureLearn): <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Gqu-Ce-OzuGj4fpbvtKPNK00WQCuqXM/edit?usp=sharing&oid=105817556365268993552&rtpof=true&sd=true>

3. SWOT analysis (Annex 3)

4. MOOC Business Canvas (Annex 4)

01_DESCRIPTION OF IDEA

EdiCitNet (Edible Cities Network – Integrating Edible City Solutions for social, resilient and sustainably productive cities) is a project funded by the European Commission and running from September 2018 to February 2024. The project aims to include the whole chain of urban food production, distribution and utilisation for inclusive urban regeneration and address societal challenges such as mass urbanisation, social inequality and climate change and resource protection in cities. The project focuses on making cities around the world better places to live through the real-life implementation and institutional integration of Edible City Solutions (ECS), and it is unique through bringing urban agriculture stakeholders, such as governance, civic society and researchers together.

MOOC (massive open online course) is a deliverable within the project for and about the Edible City Solutions. Presenting the research, activities and lessons learned from the past 5 (project) years for initiatives, municipalities, businesses and private persons to deepen their knowledge, provide them with information and inspiration and offering them a platform for networking.

02_VISION & MISSION

We want people to have a better quality of life through ECS.

We want all cities in the EU above 100.000 inhabitants to create a strategy regarding ECS.

We want edible city initiatives to sustain over a longer period of time (and not disappear).

We want to see a growth in our network by 20%.

We want to foster the production of fruit and vegetables in cities (like in Singapur, where 30% of the total fruit & veg. consumption is coming from city).

We want to make Edible City Solutions understandable for the whole society by creating a free-of-charge course, which supports participants with knowledge, inspires, empowers and gives concrete tools for developing their local Edible City Solutions and Edible City Initiatives. We want to create a network of like-minded people interested in and working on Edible City Solutions and Initiatives.

- We want to create a Master curricula at IRITHESys based on this knowledge.
- "The ECS curricula follows the principles of inclusive communities of knowledge and practice." (EdiCitNet deliverable D 7.4)

5. Multiple workshops on target audiences and learning outcomes of the course :

4.1 Target audiences workshop (Annex 5)

What we will talk about during the workshop:

We will create the "buyer personas" whom we would like to target with our MOOC:

- **Who they are:** imagined name, geography, age, family status, occupation, education, happiness with their job
- **What are their interests:** hobbies, etc.
- **What are their values?** goals & motivation?
- **What are their roles:** decision maker? influencer?
- **What actions do they prefer to take:** what are they pain points? questions they are interested about? what are their barriers and challenges?
- **What skillset are they the looking for?** what assessment would they be happy about? practical? (eg. setting up an own project?) or rather quizzes? what should students know or be able to do at the end of this course?

"By the end of this course students will be able to [ACTIVE VERB]..."

This model useful for two reasons:

- by using active verbs, we articulate actions that students will be able to do.

These actions can be observed and compared with our desired results;

- it puts the focus on students (note: it is not "By the end the course the instructor will have..."), and advances the ultimate goal of backward design—to facilitate learning, not simply to "cover" content.

Fatma

Age	Geography	Economics	Education	Family
60	Eisenkochen Germany	working class	secondary school	large family with 4 kids and 5 grandkids

Ralph

Age	Geography	Economics	Education	Family
35	Malmö Sweden	middle class	academic	single

Review

Ina: computer-savvy

Ina: want to set up a start-up

Goals	Needs & desires	Barriers and challenges
Gardening (has own allotment garden), Family, Food, Community, being able to have traditional ingredients for feeding her family, simple, mundane, Growing good quality vegetables (non industrial)	financial stability and profitability	she has plans, ideas and knowledge but needs help consulting and institutional support

Pain points: a network of ECL learn about what is happening in her location.

Needs & desires: financial stability and profitability

Barriers and challenges: she has plans, ideas and knowledge but needs help consulting and institutional support

Review

Goals	Needs & desires	Barriers and challenges
gardening, climbing, political activism, giving children important life skills, engaging with people politically, make the world a better place, taking part in activists and gardening groups, Motivation	networking, getting knowledge about gardening in schools	Barriers & challenges: working with parents

Pain points:

Needs & desires: networking, getting knowledge about gardening in schools

Barriers and challenges: working with parents

4.2 Intended Learning Outcomes workshop (Annex 6)

Backward design

Source: <https://ll.mit.edu/teaching-resources/course-design/backward-design/>

"Backward Design" is an approach to creating curriculum, subjects, and even single class sessions that treats the goal of teaching as not merely "covering" a certain amount of content, but also facilitating student learning. Backward design prioritizes the *intended learning outcomes* instead of topics to be covered. (Wiggins and McTighe, 2005) **It is thus "backward" from traditional design because instead of starting with the content to be covered, the textbook to be used, or even the test to be passed, you begin with the goals.**

- 1. Identify desired results:** intended learning outcomes (ILOs). Even if you have not articulated them explicitly, you have some set of goals and some image of what succeeding at those goals looks like. Ask yourself: what should students know or be able to do at the end of this course? (Lang, 2010)
"By the end of this course students will be able to [ACTIVE VERB]..."
This model useful for two reasons:
(1) by using *active* verbs, we articulate actions that students will be able to do. These actions can be *observed* and compared with our desired results;
(2) it puts the focus on *students* (note: it is not "By the end the course the instructor will have..."), and advances the ultimate goal of backward design—to facilitate learning, not simply to "cover" content.
- 1. Determine acceptable evidence:** With a sense of your desired results, you can then consider "acceptable evidence" of obtaining these results, the measures you use to determine whether a student's performance meets the goals you have for them. This evidence is often gathered through **assessments: exams, projects, and assignments**
- 2. Plan learning activities:** "Learning activities," then are what you do with students to help them achieve the desired results. These are the **lectures you give or the activities and practices you facilitate.**

1	Format	Link (pre)	Title	Topic/Description	Contributors	1_Gen eral	2_In	3_C	4_G	5_B	6_Pi	Time	Link	Link 2	Link 3	Transcrip	
65	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	How to organise a "Diamond Model" workshop	- What is the diamond model - how to use it - more information - benefits of organising a	Laura Martinez (Nabolaogshager),			1	1	1						
66	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	How to organise a community fruit harvesting event	Preparation – materials – infrastructure – location – catering – what to do with the	Kai Gldhrom (Mundraub)			1	1							
67	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	How to organize community seed and plant swaps	guide for hosting swap meets for either seeds or vegetable plants – best practices –	Helene Gallis (Nabolaogshager),			1	1							
68	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	How to prune and propagate shrubs and woody plants	- Why should you prune? – types of cuttings - Historical fun facts – instructions how to	Laura Martinez (Nabolaogshager),			1	1							
69	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	How to set up a community compost scheme	What is community composting? – can I set one up too? – Who is involved? – How does it work?	Ruth Smart (Brighton and Hove Food Partnership)			1	1							
70	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	Make your own skin care products from Calendula	- Historical fun facts – instructions how to make calendula oil – other skin care uses –	Helene Gallis (Nabolaogshager),			1	1							
71	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	Making and selling savory herb syrup	- What is savory – instructions how to make savory syrup – materials needed – how to sell it – conversation – how to use it	Paula Firmbach (Prinzessinnengärten Berlin, Senat)			1	1							
72	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Barriers & Opportunities to more Edible	Workshop objectives – workshop set-up – materials – steps – how to adapt it to online –	Ruth Smart (BHFP)			1	1							
73	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	Setting up a community cookery school	Finding a venue – how does it work – work with volunteers – pricing your classes –	Ruth Smart (BHFP)			1	1							
74	Factsheet	PDF	LINK	Urban foraging: Is food grown in cities safe to eat?	Foraging in the city – soil pollutants – results – recommendations	Kai Gldhrom (Mundraub)			1	1							
75	Final Project Meeti	Video+Pre	LINK	The EdiciNet Platform and Network	Highlights and Outcomes The EdiciNet Platform and Network – an interactive presentation	Josep Puyeu-Ros (ICRA), Nataša Alanasova (UJ), Ajda Caroline Nevejan (City Science)					1	0:57:06	https://youtu.be/AYV75z6VF7feat	https://box.hu-berlin.de/lib/ray/119be2f5-3d18-49b1-9b51-603a7a96f4ab7f1c		https://doc	
76	Final Project Meeti	Video+Pre	LINK	City Science Initiative and Food Strategy Berlin	City Science Initiative and Food Strategy Berlin	Inken Schmitz (Berlin Senate)					1	0:55:20	https://youtu.be/vR15bV94A7feat	https://box.hu-berlin.de/lib/ray/119be2f5-3d18-49b1-9b51-603a7a96f4ab7f1c		https://doc	
77	Final Project Meeti	Video+Pre	LINK	Stories from the EdiciNet Cities (part 1) Successes and challenges	Stories from the EdiciNet Cities - Successes and Challenges: Inken Schmitz – Berlin	Anneli Karlsson (City of Andernach), Paul					1	0:57:25	https://youtu.be/RnaW4xniP7feat	https://box.hu-berlin.de/lib/ray/119be2f5-3d18-49b1-9b51-603a7a96f4ab7f1c		https://doc	
78	Final Project Meeti	Video+Pre	LINK	Stories from the EdiciNet Cities (part 2)	Stories from the EdiciNet Cities - Successes and Challenges: Anneli Karlsson (City of Andernach), Paul	Klaus Fichter (Borderstep), Alexander Schabel					1	0:33:32	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bJ8tKfHynAAlst=Pm5HeTHGcH_wrd5AFJdSwn7iZ8GJuX8Inde	Presentation: https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/EdiBil		https://doc	
79	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Video + 2 presentations	LINK	Measure and Manage the Impact of Your Edible City Initiative Dr. Klaus Fichter, Borderstep	Measuring and managing impact is a fundamental part of running a sustainable urban food initiative, no matter what type of	Felix Möhlenhauer (BuGG), Anneli Karlsson (City of Andernach)					1	0:41:47	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ufhVRL234	Sides BUUG: https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/EdiBil		ENG VIDEO: https://doc	
80	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Video + 2 presentations	LINK	Finding Suitable Space in Urban Areas for your Edible City Initiative (GER with ENG subtitles)	More and more people are producing, selling and distributing food in the city, thus strengthening social cohesion and local economies. In many cities around the world	Idil Akdos (Nabolaogshager), Alexander Schabel					1	0:22:56	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LzK650v5Y	Sides: https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/EdiBil		https://doc	
81	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Workshop video	LINK	Founding an Edible City Initiative: First steps to kick-start your entrepreneurial	Do you want to develop a solution for supporting sustainable food production and	Alice Bischof (Wageningen)					1	00:15:14	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1MSoc44t48t=Pm5HeTHGcH_wrd5AFJdSwn7iZ8GJuX8Inde	Presentation?		https://doc	
82	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Video workshop	LINK	Maximising Impact in Your Urban Agriculture Business // Growing Jobs in	This workshop aimed to facilitate exchange among practitioners working at urban	Alice Bischof (Wageningen)					1	0:32:48	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EVqapNrf9UkUlist=Pm5HeTHGcH_wrd5AFJdSwn7iZ8GJuX8Inde	Diamond Model Guide: https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/Edible_Cities_Network_2018.pdf	Paper on: How	https://doc	
83	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Method, handbook, presentation	LINK	The Diamond Model: Analysing & Strategising for Strong, Stable & Sustainable Urban Agriculture	The Diamond Model Canvas is supporting	Alice Bischof (Wageningen)					1	0:32:48	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EVqapNrf9UkUlist=Pm5HeTHGcH_wrd5AFJdSwn7iZ8GJuX8Inde	Diamond Model Guide: https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/Edible_Cities_Network_2018.pdf	Paper on: How	https://doc	
84	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Presentati on	LINK	Finding suitable funding sources (Finanzierungsmöglichkeiten für	Finding suitable funding sources for edible city solutions can feel overwhelming. To help	Alexander Schabel (Borderstep), Laura Martinez (Nabolaogshager),					1		https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/Edible_Cities_Network_2018.pdf				
85	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Presentati on	LINK	Finding Sustainable Economic Models in Urban Agriculture: Focusing	How you spend your limited time matters. In this workshop, participants looked at how to	Laura Martinez (Nabolaogshager),					1		https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/EdiciNet_Workshop_3_Finding_Sustainable_Economic_Models_in_Urban_Agriculture_Identifying_and_Communicating_Your_Story.pdf				
86	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Presentati on	LINK	Finding Sustainable Economic Models in Urban Agriculture: Identifying and	Urban food production is essential in the transition to more sustainable cities.	Idil Akdos (Nabolaogshager),					1		https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/EdiciNet_Workshop_1_Finding_Sustainable_Economic_Models_in_Urban_Agriculture_Identifying_and_Communicating_Your_Story.pdf				
87	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Handbook	LINK	Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture // The Edible City Solutions Canvas	It is not easy to survive as an Edible City Scout (ECS) or Initiative under immense	Idil Akdos (Nabolaogshager),					1		https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/EdiciNet_Workshop_1_Finding_Sustainable_Economic_Models_in_Urban_Agriculture_Identifying_and_Communicating_Your_Story.pdf	https://www.edicinet.com/wp-content/uploads/EdiciNet_Workshop_1_Finding_Sustainable_Economic_Models_in_Urban_Agriculture_Identifying_and_Communicating_Your_Story.pdf			
88	Guides/helpful info for Edible City Initiatives	Presentati on	LINK	How to use Social Media Tools in an Effective Way	Young city farmers – A handbook for working with youth and urban	Natalie Keene (District Gamie)					1		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1Jhm7iCvos8t=Pm5HeTHGcH_wrd5AFJdSwn7iZ8GJuX8Inde	How to make a "Wicking Bed" https://youtu.be/9z9Q	How to make a "White Oil" https://www.abc.net.au/g		
89	Kids educational materials	Oslo materials	LINK	Edible Cities Activity Book - A Collection of Fun Edible City Activities for Under 10s	Andermach is a small city located around 45km south of Bonn, in the westerly Rheinland-Palatinate region of Germany. It	Xiaoqi Song (HU Berlin)					1		https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/9e0d5f3b273043508a50/				
90	Living Lab showcases + posters	Leaflet/pdf	LINK	Berlin	Berlin (3,644,826 (2018) inhabitants, the capital and biggest city in Germany, is a growing city. There is a high demand for	Xiaoqi Song (HU Berlin)					1		https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/9e0d5f3b273043508a50/				
91	Living Lab showcases + posters	Leaflet/pdf	LINK	Oslo	Oslo (699,827 inhabitants), the capital of Norway is one of the fastest growing cities in Europe, in the face of rapid development.	Xiaoqi Song (HU Berlin)					1		https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/9e0d5f3b273043508a50/				
92	Living Lab showcases + posters	Leaflet/pdf	LINK	Rotterdam	The living lab in Rotterdam is different to other Edible Cities Network Living Labs, in that it doesn't exist in a geographical location. Instead, it operates as the umbrella	Xiaoqi Song (HU Berlin)					1		https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/9e0d5f3b273043508a50/				
93	Masterplans	Handbook	LINK	Berlin "Essbare Kieze" document	Practical and interactive support in the implementation of edible city solutions in	Inken Schmitz (City of Berlin), Tina H					1		https://box.hu-berlin.de/18ccbec874e47caa597/				
94	NEW: Masterplanning	Factsheet	LINK	How to become an Edible City	How to become an Edible City is a process which can have many starting points from	Marieke Piepenburg, 3IN social scd					1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/				
95	NEW: Masterplanning	Factsheet	LINK	How the Masterplans were developed	In this document you can find a short overview about the Masterplan development	Marieke Piepenburg, 3IN social scd					1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/				
96	NEW: Masterplanning	Factsheet	LINK	Masterplanning in Berlin	An Edible City set-up in the framework of an urban renewal program.	Marieke Piepenburg, 3IN social scd					1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/				
97	NEW: Masterplanning	Factsheet	LINK	Masterplanning in Carthage	Growing an Edible City within and around areas protected by the	Marieke Piepenburg, 3IN social scd					1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/				
98	NEW: Masterplanning	Factsheet	LINK	Masterplanning in Guangzhou	Promoting safe, stable and efficient food supply in the city, while encouraging	Marieke Piepenburg, 3IN social scd					1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/				
99	NEW: Masterplanning	Factsheet	LINK	Masterplanning in Lomé - Gulf 2	Focusing on the overall urban development of the municipality with strong connections to the Edible City and proposing new futures to	Marieke Piepenburg, 3IN social scd					1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/				
100	NEW: Masterplanning	Factsheet	LINK	Masterplanning in Montevideo	Answering to strong social problems and a lack of green spaces, the Edible City is set up in the framework of the program "Plantar es	Marieke Piepenburg, 3IN social scd					1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/				
101	NEW: Masterplanning	Factsheet	LINK	Masterplanning in Sempeter-Vrtojba	An Edible City developed within a small town with an active community.	Marieke Piepenburg, 3IN social scd					1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/				
102	NEW: Masterplanning	Factsheet	LINK	Masterplanning in Sant Felu de Llobregat	Resolving environmental and societal challenges through the set-up of an Edible City on the riverbank of the	Marieke Piepenburg, 3IN social scd					1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/				
103	NEW: BHFP	Factsheet	LINK	How to create a podcast?	The Brighton & Hove Food Partnership created a podcast called "Making Cities	Edible Cities in our cities, our communities.					1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/reso/2019/02/24/			
104	NEW: BHFP	Podcast	Spotify	Making cities edible - Heritage and history in Ljubljana's Food System with Maruška Markovič	In this conversation, we speak to Maruška Markovič, the Senior Advisor for the Department of Environmental Protection and	Maruška Markovič (Department of Environmental Protection and					1	1:00:00				https://doc	
105	NEW: BHFP	Podcast	Spotify	Making cities edible - Shaping Space, Shaping Society with Helene Gallis	In this episode of the podcast Making Cities Edible, we speak to Helene Gallis, community strategist and placemaker for	Helene Gallis (Nabolaogshager)					1	1				https://doc	
106	NEW: BHFP	Podcast	Spotify	Making cities edible	In this episode we speak to Toni Karge, a Berlin-based town planner who works for the Berlin Senate Department for the	Toni Karge (Senate of Berlin)					1	1:00:00				https://doc	
107	NEW: BHFP	Podcast	Spotify	Making cities edible - Growing food and growing connections with Caroline Zeevat	In this episode we speak to Caroline Zeevat, a green social entrepreneur based in Rotterdam and one of the founding members of the Groen10 network. Groen10 brings	Caroline Zeevat (Groen10)					1	1	1:00:00			https://doc	

1	Format	Link (prec)	Title	Topic/Description	Contributors	1_Gen_eral	2_In	3_C	4_G	5_B	6_Pt	Time	Link	Link 2	Link 3	Transcr
127	New: Fragment	Presentati on	LINK	"Journalism and communication for ECS initiatives"	Appearing in the (local) news is not always easy. In our masterclass we compiled knowledge especially for edible city initiatives	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/226			
128	New: Fragment	Factsheet	LINK	"Journalism and communication for ECS initiatives"	Appearing in the (local) news is not always easy. Get to know how the media works and learn how to create a newsworthy event!	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/227			
129	New: Fragment	Factsheet	LINK	"Journalism and communication for ECS initiatives"	Appearing in the (local) news is not always easy. Get to know how the media works and learn how to create a newsworthy event!	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/228			
130	New: Fragment	Factsheet	LINK	"Journalism and communication for ECS initiatives"	Appearing in the (local) news is not always easy. Get to know how the media works and learn how to create a newsworthy event!	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/229			
131	New: Fragment	Video	Link	Sustainable economic models in urban agriculture"	Most Edible City Initiatives are aiming for a positive change, regardless of business or non-profit model. Even the most basic setup.	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1	0:32:07	https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/221			
132	New: Fragment	Presentati on	LINK	"Sustainable economic models in urban agriculture"	Most Edible City Initiatives are aiming for a positive change, regardless of business or non-profit model. Even the most basic setup.	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/221			
133	New: Fragment	Factsheet	LINK	"Sustainable economic models in urban agriculture"	Most Edible City Initiatives are aiming for a positive change, regardless of business or non-profit model. Even the most basic setup.	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/222			
134	New: Fragment	Factsheet	LINK	"Sustainable economic models in urban agriculture"	Most Edible City Initiatives are aiming for a positive change, regardless of business or non-profit model. Even the most basic setup.	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/223			
135	New: Fragment	Factsheet	LINK	"Sustainable economic models in urban agriculture"	Most Edible City Initiatives are aiming for a positive change, regardless of business or non-profit model. Even the most basic setup.	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/224			
136	New: Fragment	Factsheet	Link	"Sustainable economic models in urban agriculture"	Most Edible City Initiatives are aiming for a positive change, regardless of business or non-profit model. Even the most basic setup.	Helene Gallis (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/225			
137	New: Fragment	Video	Link	Cultivating public spaces	Local food initiatives are mostly met with enthusiasm from municipalities. Low public budgets can make it difficult for the municipality to contribute, making projects	Helene Gallis, Anil Eriksen (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1	0:26:11	https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/219			
138	New: Fragment	Presentati on	LINK	Cultivating public spaces	Local food initiatives are mostly met with enthusiasm from municipalities. Low public budgets can make it difficult for the municipality to contribute, making projects	Helene Gallis, Anil Eriksen (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/219			
139	New: Fragment	Factsheet	Link	Cultivating public spaces	Local food initiatives are mostly met with enthusiasm from municipalities. Low public budgets can make it difficult for the municipality to contribute, making projects	Helene Gallis, Anil Eriksen (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/217			
140	New: Fragment	Factsheet	Link	Cultivating public spaces	Local food initiatives are mostly met with enthusiasm from municipalities. Low public budgets can make it difficult for the municipality to contribute, making projects	Helene Gallis, Anil Eriksen (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/218			
1																
141	NEW: GROEN 010	Video	LINK	How to grow a network?	How Rotterdam's Living Lab was developed together with Nienke Bouwhuis (De Groene Connectie) - https://www.jointhegroen010network.com	Nienke Bouwhuis (De Groene Connectie), Paul de Groen010			1	1	1	0:05:35	https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/230			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/230
142	NEW: GROEN 010	Factsheet	Link	How to grow a network?	How Rotterdam's Living Lab was developed together with Nienke Bouwhuis (De Groene Connectie) - https://www.jointhegroen010network.com	Green010			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/230	Factsheet Groen010_CAMPAIGN-2		
143	New: Fragment	Factsheet	Link	Cultivating public spaces	Local food initiatives are mostly met with enthusiasm from municipalities. Low public budgets can make it difficult for the municipality to contribute, making projects	Helene Gallis, Anil Eriksen (FRAGMENT, Norway)			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/218			
144	NEW: GROEN 010	Video	LINK	How to lobby?	"By working together in this Living Lab, we soon discovered what is the key to the success of Rotterdam's green initiatives." Watch our film on How to lobby? here: https://youtu.be/0a1111111111	Marja Versteeg (Stadswerken) de Kaa, Philip Kuypers			1	1	1	0:04:38	https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/231			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/231
145	NEW: GROEN 010	Factsheet	Link	How to lobby?	"By working together in this Living Lab, we soon discovered what is the key to the success of Rotterdam's green initiatives." Watch our film on How to lobby? here: https://youtu.be/0a1111111111	Green010			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/231	Factsheet Groen010_LOBBY-2.pdf		
146	NEW: GROEN 010	Video	LINK	How to start a campaign?	What if Rotterdam was becoming a National Park City? Watch our video on How to start a campaign? here: https://youtu.be/0a1111111111	Marlen Arkesteijn (Stadsboeren Rotterdam)			1	1	1	0:05:52	https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/233			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/233
147	NEW: GROEN 010	Factsheet	Link	How to start a campaign?	What if Rotterdam was becoming a National Park City? Watch our video on How to start a campaign? here: https://youtu.be/0a1111111111	Green010			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/233	Factsheet Groen010_CAMPAIGN-2.pdf		
148	NEW: GROEN 010	Video	LINK	Networking in Practice	The green initiatives in Rotterdam proved that they can be part of Green010 network and join their newsletter! Watch our video on Networking in Practice: https://youtu.be/0a1111111111	Meriam Beek (Voedselstun) Marja Versteeg			1	1	1	0:05:06	https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/232			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/232
149	NEW: GROEN 010	Factsheet	Link	Networking in Practice	The green initiatives in Rotterdam proved that they can be part of Green010 network and join their newsletter! Watch our video on Networking in Practice: https://youtu.be/0a1111111111	Green010			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/232	Factsheet Groen010_SHARINGKNOWLEDGE-2.pdf		
150	NEW: GROEN 010	Video	LINK	Visibility and value	How to recognise the values of your green initiative? Watch our video on Visibility and Value: https://youtu.be/0a1111111111	Anne Karin ten Bosch (Volkskultuurvereniging Bildorp)			1	1	1	0:05:14	https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/234			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/234
151	NEW: GROEN 010	Factsheet	LINK	Visibility and value	How to recognise the values of your green initiative? Watch our video on Visibility and Value: https://youtu.be/0a1111111111	Green010			1	1	1		https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/234			
151	NEW: Oslo	Video + Presentati on	Link	Urban Food Production - An Incubator Programme to Boost Entrepreneurship	Why is urban agriculture and urban food production so important? Why should cities take responsibility to create greener and edibler cities? During the EdiciNet project,	Stephanie Degenhardt			1	1	1	0:22:00				
1																
164	New: Video	video	LINK	What are edible cities? - A conversation between our partners	In this video we are discussing the basic terminology of edible cities to with the aim to cater the diverse learning styles among	Caroline Zeevat (Green010), Sbei Hanen (REACT)			1			0:38:05	https://youtu.be/F12V2NwCid0			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235
165	New: Video for promotion	video	https://youtu.be/ka	What is an edible city?	An "edible city" emphasises the integration of food-producing elements into the urban landscape, promoting local and sustainable								https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235
166	New: Video for promotion	video	https://youtu.be/05	What are the missing elements for growing food in cities?	Not all people have the opportunity and the mentality to grow food in their cities. What are these factors and how can you overcome								https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235
167	New: Video for promotion	video	https://youtu.be/1f	Growing your own food on your balcony	Did you know that growing herbs, flowers and vegetables on the smallest balconies helps to increase biodiversity in the cities? But why is								https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235
168	New: Video for promotion	video	https://youtu.be/nx	How to be connected with food?	Think about what connection you have with the food you are eating? Is it coming from the supermarket? Imagine how different it would								https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235
169	New: Video for promotion	video	https://youtu.be/N	How is it to grow food in a community garden?	What are the pros and cons of a community garden? How is it to grow food in urban spaces - where half of the crops will be								https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235
170	New: Video for promotion	video	https://youtu.be/Re	The importance of growing individuals into an organisation	Are you an individual interested in edible cities? Are you part of an edible city initiative, struggling to be seen by your local								https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235			https://ediblecitiesnetwork.com/resource/235
172	Other	Video	Link	Ina Samuel MOOC Intro					1			0:15:16				
173	Other	Video	Link	Edible Cities Network Oslo Living Lab Linderud - Anne Lyth, chairman, Linderud Community Garden	Interview with Anne Lyth, chairman, Linderud Community Garden, member of the Edible Cities Network Living Lab in Oslo. The	Anne Lyth (Linderud Community Garden)				1		0:06:28				
174	Other	Video	Link	Co-creation of NBS for multifunctional, resilient and healthy landscapes? Ina Samuel's presentation	The lecture is organized by Zhifang Wang (PKU - Peking University). The guest speaker is Xin Wang, Assistant Professor from	Zhifang Wang (PKU - Peking University), Xin Wang (Shangdong University) and Bining Huang (Sketch Action).										
175	Other	Video	Link	Edible Cities Network Oslo Living Lab Linderud - Bålprat "Campfire chat"	Interview with Bålprat "Campfire chat" is a member of the Edible Cities Network Living Lab in Oslo. "Campfire chat" is an umbrella	Bålprat				1		0:04:05				
176	Other	Video	Link	Edible Cities Network Oslo Living Lab Linderud - Natur Videregående (Nature High School)	Interview with Natur Videregående (Nature High School), member of the Edible Cities Network Living Lab in Oslo about the	Natur Videregående				1		0:05:10				
177	Other	Video	Link	Edible Cities Network Oslo Living Lab Linderud - Slåttemark	Interview with Slåttemark, the Natural History Museum, member of the Edible Cities Network Living Lab in Oslo. The museum's botanists, with the help of the students from the Nature High school, planted a flower							0:08:35				

1	Format	Link (precise)	Title	Topic/Description	Contributors	1_General	2_In	3_C	4_G	5_B	6_PI	Time	Link	Link 2	Link 3	Transc	
212	Publication	PDF	LINK	Diverse business models support urban farming and food marketing in Bristol	The City of Bristol has a long history and well-established practices in urban farming and city food system planning. Farms apply	Sebastian Eiler (NIBIO), Daniel Keach (University of					1						
214	Publication	PDF	LINK	Monitoring Motivations for Urban Gardening	Over three years, motivations of participants in a neighbourhood garden seemed to reflect the development of the garden from the	Ingrid Renning Heyerdahl (NIBIO), Juditte Juel Dab					1	1					
215	Publication	PDF	LINK	Monitoring people's motivations to participate in an urban neighbourhood and community garden	Participation in Lindenud neighbourhood and community garden in Oslo is mostly motivated by social aspects and by the desire	Sebastian Eiler (NIBIO), Wendy Fjellstad (NIBIO), Pia					1	1					
216	Publication	PDF	LINK	More cooperation and targeted support can increase production and sales of local vegetables in Bergen	There are few local, small-scale vegetable producers selling their products in Bergen today. In order to obtain input on how such	Anna Birgitte Milford (NIBIO), Mari Steverud Beltnes					1						
217	Publication	PDF	LINK	Roadsides - habitat for many plant species and pollinating insects (Norwegian)	Roadsides are often overlooked and underestimated as biologically important areas. But even though they are narrow, they	Christian Pedersen, Wenche Dramstad					1	1					
218	Publication	PDF	LINK	Strategy for increased food production in Gjemnes municipality (Norwegian)	Increased food production based on Norwegian resources is a well-known objective in Norwegian agricultural policy, but	Idri Kristine (Rose) Bergslid (NIBIO)					1						
219	Publication	PDF	LINK	Tertiary vocational education - Sustainable food experiences (Norwegian)	New education meets new challenges	Eva Narten Høberg					1						
220	Publication	PDF	LINK	The effect of compost in cultivated soil (Norwegian)	Compost is produced through the conversion of organically degradable material under good air access. The composting process is	B. Føred, O. Bergersen, R. Sæviem					1	1	1				
221	Publication	PDF	LINK	Urban agriculture - For everyone and everywhere? (Norwegian)	Researchers in the European COST network "Urban Agriculture Europe" have developed a common conceptual framework as a basis for	Sebastian Eiler (NIBIO)					1						
222	Publication	PDF	LINK	Urban agriculture: "Everyone" can contribute to increased food security in Norway (Norwegian)	A calculation example for Oslo shows that private, small-scale and non-commercial cultivation in cities can increase Norwegian	Maria Pettersen (NMBU), Trine Hvoslef-Eide					1	1					
223	Publication	PDF	LINK	Urban gardening contributes to health and quality of life	Participating in a neighbourhood and community garden has positive social and emotional impacts, as well as the satisfaction	Kristine Valle (NIBIO), Eli Mari Øverdråh, (NIBIO), Sebastian Eiler					1						
224	Publication	PDF	LINK	Vegetables and belonging: allotment gardens provide healthy food and well-being (Norwegian)	Growers get 'double' benefits from their garden in the form of fresh fruit and vegetables, and social fellowship. The least	Sebastian Eiler (NIBIO), Esther J. Veen (Wageningen University)					1	1	1				

1	Format	Link (precise)	Title	Topic/Description	Contributors	1_General	2_In	3_C	4_G	5_B	6_PI	Time	Link	Link 2	Link 3	Transc		
225	Publication	PDF	LINK	WebGIS wastewater, a professional system for wastewater treatment plants	WebGIS wastewater is a professional system for private wastewater solutions in the municipalities. The application calculates	Stein Turtumøygaard, Guro Randem Hensel					1	1	1					
226	Publication	PDF	LINK	What is the state of the city's green space? (Norwegian)	More and more Norwegians live and work in cities and towns. The need for new buildings is therefore great, which means that green	Jutta Kapfer (NIBIO), Wendy Fjellstad (NIBIO)					1							
227	Publication	PDF	LINK	Use of biochar for green roofs (Norwegian)	Green roofs are increasingly being used to meet the challenges of extreme rainfall and stormwater management in cities and towns.	Pierre-Adrien Rivier (NIBIO), Hans Martin Hanalin (NIBIO), Erik					1	1	1					
230	Summer school sessions 2021	Video + presentation	LINK	ECS & Society Marisa Pettit, EdiciNet Vic Borrill, Director, BHFP	What is a Food Partnership? What food strategies are and how we use them? What food strategy thinking can bring	Marisa Pettit (HU Berlin) Vic Borrill (BHFP) Ruth Smart					1	1	1	1	1:21:12	Youtube	Vic_Presentation Ruth Presentation: https://docs.google.com/p	Community Co ONLINE: https://
231	Summer school sessions 2021	Video + presentation +	LINK	ECS & Ecology Presentations (2) on ecological aspects of ECS - especially water.	To understand the importance of closed-loop systems, ecosystem services, and urban (agro) biodiversity and related ecological	Martin Regelsberger (TO), Latifa Bousselmi (REACT)					1	1	1	1:49:53	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0V9H4QFX3E&feature=youtu.be	Martin Presentation: https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/bed256a148ed4e83ad14/	https://	
232	Summer school sessions 2021	Video + presentation	LINK	ECS & Policy Felix Mollenhauer (BUGG) https://youtu.be/RebeccaMolke (BUGG) https://youtu.be/	1. Who and what is BUGG? Felix Mollenhauer (BUGG), Rebecca Molke (BUGG),	Felix Mollenhauer (BUGG), Rebecca Molke (BUGG),					1		2:11:00	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QJmVWhoOpam	https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/66f2343d455f42d959bc2/	https://		
233	Summer school sessions 2021	presentation on Video2	LINK	ECS & Economy	Robert talks about the background of PRINZ & the economic details	Robert Shaw (Prinzessinnengärten)							Video2	Presentation: https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/6a18d358fad9734e889e25/				
234	Summer school sessions 2021	PDFs	LINK	Task	How to set-up edible city solution 1. // A potential Edible City Solution in your City								PDF					
235	Summer school sessions 2022	Video	LINK	Flows of resources in cities	Natasa Atanasova's masterclass on resource flows and circularity in cities, the circular management of cities, cities and the climate	Natasa Atanasova (UL)					1	1	0:58:26	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IDBy3JmQe83&list=PLm5HieTHGcH_yiCI_vzRqRrRmMISGDwJ&index=3		https://		
236	Summer school sessions 2022	Video	LINK	Using roofs for urban agriculture (Felix Mollenhauer, Bundesverband Gebäudegrün - German Association of	Green Roofs Urban Agriculture Checklist	Felix Mollenhauer (BUGG)					1		0:45:30	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0hs2RkkPFA&list=PLm5HieTHGcH_yiCI_vzRqRrRmMISGDwJ&index=2	https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/3d6df289367d4e73baab/	https://		
237	Summer school sessions 2022	Video + presentation	LINK	Co-creation of NBS for multifunctional, EdiciNet Mission & Co-Creation Strategy EdiciNet Co-Creation Strategy	MULTIFUNCTIONAL LANDSCAPES LANDSCAPE SCIENCE & LANDSCAPE BIOGRAPHIES	Ina Säumel (HU Berlin)					1	1	0:45:30	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0hs2RkkPFA&list=PLm5HieTHGcH_yiCI_vzRqRrRmMISGDwJ&index=2	https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/3d6df289367d4e73baab/	https://		
238	Summer school sessions 2022	Video	LINK	The Prinzessinnengärten - Social and c	Social and cultural impact of the garden Participation, how to run an initiative as a collective History and facts Education	Robert Shaw (Prinzessinnengärten)					1	1	0:32:53	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1fhwMXJtGcQ	https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/68f99abfb84649c/	https://		

1	Format	Link (precise)	Title	Topic/Description	Contributors	1_General	2_In	3_C	4_G	5_B	6_PI	Time	Link	Link 2	Link 3	Transc
239	Summer school sessions 2022	Video	LINK	Urban greening and environmental (in)j	To get a critical lens of Environment and Society	Alexandra Popartan (LEQUIA)					1		0:28:16	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PhJbHxHtFg		https://
240	Summer school sessions 2022	PDFs	LINK	Extra reading	Environmental justice: Theory and history Extra reading on conservation, NBS from Ina etc								https://box.hu-berlin.de/d/9c8b8cc3f644055965c/		Klara	
246	Urban Agriculture workshop videos	Video	LINK	Key Resources of the initiative Gruten AS	Gruten is a Norwegian start-up, growing oyster mushrooms on coffee waste. Watch their founder Siri Mittet talking about their key	Siri Mittet (Gruten AS)						1	0:15:06	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5BCrSUKwI	NO PRESENTATION	https://
247	Urban Agriculture workshop videos	Video	LINK	Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture Integrating Outreach to your Business	How can urban agriculture businesses integrate outreach to broaden impact?	Nora May Engeseth (Food activist)						1	0:15:24	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tlGIGX6rQk	Presentation?	https://
248	Urban Agriculture workshop videos	Video	LINK	Thriving Urban Agriculture Businesses + How does CSA work?	Thriving urban agricultural businesses	Natalie Keene (Food entrepreneur)						1	0:28:43	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RsAJDkQe	Presentation?	https://
249	Urban Agriculture workshop videos	Video	LINK	Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture Who are your customers?	Who are your customers? (David Bratlie , Dugurd Kantiner, Oslo https://www.dugurdkantiner.no/, they have	David Bratlie, Dugurd Kantiner, Oslo						1	0:15:51	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sic9lsQQ8xw	NO PRESENTATION	https://
250	Urban Agriculture workshop videos	Video	LINK	Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture How to use Social Media Tools in an Effective Way	How to use Social Media Tools in an Effective Way	Stian Broch (Photographer)						1	0:16:04	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1Uhm17ICvoo	NO PRESENTATION	https://
251	Urban Agriculture workshop videos	Video	LINK	Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture // The Edible City Solutions Canvas Business Model	Maximising Impact + What is a value proposition and how does it work? (Alexander Schnabel, Borderstep) This video	Alexander Schnabel (Borderstep)						1	0:15:00	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1MSScd4d3A&list=PLm5HieTHGcH_yiCI_vzRqRrRmMISGDwJ&index=2	Presentation?	https://
252	Urban Agriculture workshop videos	Video	LINK	Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture Forging Alliances Across Disconnected Domains	Forging Alliances Across Disconnected Domains	Katrina Sjøberg (Herbanist Urban Garden)						1	0:15:00	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dqP0sA3Gs&list=PLm5HieTHGcH_yiCI_vzRqRrRmMISGDwJ&index=2	NO PRESENTATION	https://
253	Urban Agriculture workshop videos	Video	LINK	Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture Availability and Creativity	Availability and Creativity in creating and running a business	Vanessa Krogh (Vilbrygg)						1	0:15:40	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MouSiKy2c_k	Presentation?	https://
254	Urban Agriculture workshop videos	Video	LINK	Growing Jobs in Urban Agriculture // The Edible City Solutions Canvas Business Model	1. What is a value proposition and how does it work? (Alexander Schnabel, Borderstep)	Alexander Schnabel, Borderstep						1	0:15:13	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1MSScd4d3A&list=PLm5HieTHGcH_yiCI_vzRqRrRmMISGDwJ&index=2	Presentation?	https://
256	Webinar	Video	LINK	Building and sustaining inclusive green communities across cities in Europe	Learn how inclusive green communities can be established, nurtured and sustained in this online webinar, an official European Week of	Jago Dodson (RMIT), Nevelina Pachova (RMIT)						1	0:59:05	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GkAw2MfA6J4&ab_channel=EdibleCitiesNetwork	PRESENTATION	https://
257	Webinar	Video	LINK	How to engage and retain Employees and Volunteers? Employer Value Proposition								1	0:30:36	https://youtu.be/dWby9KXVY?feature=shared&t=568		https://

1	Format	Link (prec)	Title	Topic/Description	Contributors	1_Gen eral	2_ In	3_ C	4_ G	5_ B	6_ PI	Time	Link	Link 2	Link 3	Transcri	
259	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Video + presentation	LINK	(Up)scaling (Edible) Nature-Based Solutions – Experiences, Opportunities & Challenges	In cities, nature-based solutions are actions and policies that use the power of nature to help tackle environmental and social	Ina Säumel (HU Berlin), Marisa Pettit (HU Berlin), Sara		1	1	1		1:14:00	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4uWJj6AJj0	https://www.edicifnet.com/wp-content/uploads/UpScaling-Workshop-EdiCitNet		https://do	
260	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Audio file + presentation	LINK	"Food Connects Us" - How to Join Forces with City Authorities for more social, edible cities	The Brighton & Hove Food Partnership is a non-profit organisation helping people learn to cook, eat a healthy diet, grow their own	Vic Borrill (BHFP), Ruth Smart (BHFP), Angela Blair		1	1			1:00:37	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GvVwBYvL_A	Presentation: https://www.edicifnet.com/wp-content/uploads/Food-	Related video: Gold Sustainable	https://do	
261	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Video + presentation	LINK	Applying an intersectional gender lens in urban food systems planning	Gender and our food system are inextricably linked. As well as there being barriers to participation in food value chains due to	Jess Halliday (RUAF)		1	1			0:28:04	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wkTSMaE_ZM	https://www.edicifnet.com/wp-content/uplo			
262	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Video + presentation	LINK	Making cities edible with building-integrated agriculture	Building-integrated urban agriculture – like rooftop farms and edible green facades – offer cities a range of ecological.	Rebecca Gohike (BuGG), Felix Mollenhauer (BuGG)				1		0:54:35	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PFh_Ew3VYdU	https://www.edicifnet.com/wp-content/uplo			
263	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Video + presentation	LINK	Closed-Loop Urban Farming - Recycling Water & Reclaiming Nutrients	For urban food production and the environment to go hand in hand, it's important to consider the resources used	Martin Regelsberger (TO), Erwin Nolde (Nolde & Partner)		1	1	1		0:40:37	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F1ZsvD6Z5dI	https://www.edicifnet.com/wp-content/uploads/Closed-Loop-Urban-Farming-E	Related video: Flushing toilets On behalf of th	https://do	
264	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Video + presentation	LINK	Urban Beekeeping & the Benefits of Pollinators in Our Cities with Martin Stelter from Stadtbienen and Steve Setting up a Community Kitchen: Our story	The benefits of having pollinators in the city are many – including higher biodiversity and increased food security thanks to pollination. Watch Jess Crocker and Jo Giabezbrook telling the story of setting up the Brighton & Hove Food Partnership Community Kitchen!	Martin Stelter from Stadtbienen and Steve Rogenstein		1	1	1		0:35:10	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jwove6QwyOM&feature=youtu.be	https://www.edicifnet.com/wp-content/uploads/EdiCitNet-Global-Lunch-Talk-9		https://do	
266	Webinars Other	Video	LINK														
267	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Video + presentation	LINK	Bio-diversity focused community gardens and public health. Workshop: Biodiversity-focused community	Urban living is associated with multiple health risks including air pollution, heat stress, limited opportunities to be physically active	Dr. med. et med. univ. Michael Eichinger, MSc		1				0:35:02					
268	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Video + presentation	LINK	The new Edible Cities Network Platform	Over the past five years, the Edible Cities Network has tirelessly worked on the mission to make our cities greener, more sustainable	Josep Pueyo-Ros (Catalan Institute for Water Research) and				1	1	0:45:05					
269	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Video + presentation	LINK	Building a Network of Green Initiatives for Resilience and Increased Impact	In Rotterdam, the organisation Groen010 is developing a framework for engaging and organising edible green initiatives in a way	Paul de Graaf (Groen010)				1		0:33:58	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1SvTS1_BNS8	https://www.edicifnet.com/wp-content/uploads/Groening-a-Network_LivingLabB		https://do	
278	Webinars "Lunch Talks"	Video + presentation	LINK	Introduction presentation by Ina		Ina Säumel (HU Berlin)											
273	Other	Video	LINK	Agroecological Schools in Sant Feliu de	As part of the Edible Cities Network project, the city of Sant Feliu de Llobregat is working with the local council, and many other local					1		0:03:01	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=No_-8Lnh6			Subtitles	
274	Team					Edi Ivanov Emlov, Sophia Kipp, Elena											

1	Format	Link (prec)	Title	Topic/Description	Contributors	1_Gen eral	2_ In	3_ C	4_ G	5_ B	6_ PI	Time	Link	Link 2	Link 3	Trans	
275	Other Cemetery Co	Poster		Living Cemeteries	In light of traditional practices, cemeteries often exhibit poor biodiversity and inhibit ecological services. In our text we explain the	Ruhr-University Bochum: Erin Mahon, Juan David				1							
276	Other Cemetery Co	Presentation + video		Presentation		Kunstuniversität Linz in Wien: Thomas Macho				1							
277	Other Cemetery Conference			Presentation		Friedrich-Schiller-Uni versität Jena: Barbara Happe				1							
278	Other Cemetery Conference			Presentation		Universität Rostock: Jakob Kühn				1							
279	Other Cemetery Conference			Presentation		Universität Düsseldorf: Dieter Birnbacher				1							
280	Other Cemetery Conference			Presentation		Johannes Kepler Universität Linz: Anna Obereder				1							

9. MOOC Syllabus based on the ECS Knowledge Pool (Annex 9)

1. General introduction - an overview	2
1.1. What are edible cities?	2
1.2. Course Description	3
1.3. Presentation of the EdiCitNet platform and invitation to register	3
1.4. Summary	3
1.5. TASK and QUIZ	3
2. Introduction to Edible Cities	3
2.1. Brief history of urban food production: A path towards Edible Cities	3
2.2. Fundamentals and terminology	3
2.3. The impact of Edible cities on society	4
2.4. Edible cities as a measure against climate change	4
2.5. Bottom-up versus top-down approaches towards edible cities	5

2.6. RESOURCES _____	5
2.7. Summary _____	6
2.8. Quiz on History and basic Terminology _____	6
3. Community-based (bottom-up) approach _____	6
3.1. Social values addressed by ECS _____	6
3.2. Adaptation strategies for different sociocultural environments _____	7
3.3. What is scaling? (Up)scaling pathways _____	7
3.4. Practical guidelines for communities and community organizers _____	7
3.4.1. The power of people, collaboration, partnerships and networks _____	8
3.4.2. Economic considerations _____	8
3.4.3. Talking to your local politician _____	8
3.4.4. Setting up collective-work events _____	9
3.4.5. Education and research _____	10
3.4.6. Dissemination strategies _____	10
3.5. RESOURCES _____	10
3.6. Summary _____	11
3.7. Quiz and Task _____	11
4. Government-based (Top-down) approach _____	11
4.1. The benefits of becoming an edible city _____	11
4.2. Co-creation as a new (complementary) form of governance _____	11
4.3. Challenges in urban planning addressed by ECS _____	12
4.4. Governance _____	13
4.5. Education and work with youth _____	13
4.6. Practical guidelines for the city administration _____	14
4.6.1. Guidelines to governance _____	14
4.6.2. Urban planning tools _____	15
4.6.3. Building-integrated Urban Agriculture _____	15
4.6.4. Cultivating public spaces - Examples for community events and actions _____	15
4.6.5. Dissemination strategies _____	16
4.7. RESOURCES _____	16
4.8. Summary _____	17
4.9. Quiz + Task _____	17
5. Business - Ways to monetize your knowledge and create impact _____	17
5.1. Fundamentals of circular economy _____	17
5.2. Fundamentals of Social Entrepreneurship _____	17
5.3. Challenges faced by edible city entrepreneurs _____	17
5.4. What is impact? _____	17
5.5. Practical steps on starting your own business with an Edible City Solution _____	18
5.5.1. Developing your business model _____	18

5.5.2. (Up)scaling and adding a social value to your business _____	18
5.5.3. Economic considerations and evaluation methods _____	18
5.5.4. How to start a start-up? _____	18
5.5.5. The power of people. How can collaboration and co-creation increase the success and sustainability of a project? _____	19
5.5.6. Adaptation strategies for different political and business ecosystems _____	19
5.5.7. Dissemination strategies _____	20
5.6. RESOURCES _____	20
5.7. Summary _____	20
5.8. Quiz + Task _____	20
6. Practical guidelines to make cities edible _____	20
7. The EdicitNet Platform (Extracurricular) _____	21
7.1. The importance of a social network _____	21
7.2. How-to: design and plan your edible city solution (New) _____	21
7.3. How-to: sustainability assessment tool (New) _____	21
7.4. How-to: network (create your profile!) (New) _____	21
7.5. Introducing some members and initiatives (New) _____	21
7.6. How to create solutions, initiatives, your own profile etc. (New) _____	21
8. Conclusion _____	21
8.1. Summary _____	21
8.2. Discussion: Forum _____	21
8.4. FAQ _____	22

Glossary

Abbreviation	Description
CMT	Community Management Tool
CS	Citizen Science
DEP	Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
DCEP	Dissemination, Communication and Education Plan
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
ECS	Edible City Solutions
EMJMDs	Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degrees
EU	European Union
FRC	Front Runner City
FC	Follower City
GA	Grant Agreement
GNU GPL	GNU General Public Licence, is a series of widely used free software licenses or copyleft that guarantee end users the four freedoms to run, study, share, and modify the software
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
LMS	Learning Management System
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MUFPP	Milan Urban Food Policy Pact
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PHP	Abbreviation of Personal Home Page, PHP is a general-purpose scripting language geared towards web development
SE	Social Entrepreneur
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
Telcos	Telecommunication Meetings
WP	Work Package

About the EdiCitNet project

EdiCitNet is demonstrating innovative Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). **Edible City Solutions** are going one step further: We include the whole chain of urban food production, distribution and utilisation for **inclusive urban regeneration** and address societal challenges such as mass urbanisation, social inequality and climate change and resource protection in cities. The key components (1) **City Teams**, (2) **Living Labs**, (3) **Masterplans** and the (4) **Edible Cities Network Platform** provide the basic structure of EdiCitNet.

Thank you! www.ediblecitiesnetwork.com

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Reports in #openaccess #OA in Zenodo
<https://zenodo.org/communities/edicitnet/>